

SPEECH CULTURE AS A COMPONENT OF PROFESSIONAL PREPARING FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682676>

Abstract. *The development of a culture of professional communication between future primary school teachers is a very relevant topic. The formation of a culture of speech among students studying at universities of the Republic can be complicated by insufficient knowledge of the Uzbek language. Thus, each subject teacher must contribute to this process and act in agreement with the entire teaching staff. In practice, this does not always happen. In order to develop communication skills, students acquire skills to develop a culture of speech with the help of various forms and methods of work in all classes in the process of studying each subject of the curriculum.*

Keywords: *speech, language norms, students, communicative and speech competence, Uzbek literary language, future primary school teacher.*

Bunder the current conditions, higher education should become flexible, highly adaptable, allowing to graduate highly qualified specialists who are ready for self-development, think critically and creatively, who can competently convey information using correct, expressive, figurative speech. These factors predetermine the need for the formation and development of general cultural, general professional and professional competencies. Changes in the content of vocational training correspond to temporary realities, the achievements of science, and must take into account a number of conditions: – strengthening connection with life, theories with practice; – integration of all components of the professional sional training; – determination of the necessary ratio knowledge of general pedagogical, philological and special orientation.

As part of the development of the native language, the Federal State Educational Standard of Primary General Education assumes:

- 1) the formation of initial preideas about the unity and diversity of the linguistic and cultural space of Uzbek, about language as the basis of national self-consciousness;
- 2) students' understanding of what language is a phenomenon of national culture and the main means of human communication, awareness of the importance of the Russian language as the state language of the Uzbek, the language of interethnic communication;
- 3) the formation of a positive attitude decisions to correct oral and written speech as indicators of the general culture and civic position of a person;
- 4) mastery of the initial ideas decisions about the norms of the Uzbek and native literary language (orthoepic, lexical, grammatical) and the rules of speech etiquette; the ability to navigate the goals, objectives, means and conditions of communication, to choose adequate language tools for the successful solution of communicative tasks;
- 5) mastery of learning activities with the language basic units and the ability to use knowledge to solve cognitive, practical and communicative problems.

The main objectives of the implementation of the content of the subject area "Philology" are: the formation of initial ideas about the unity and diversity of the linguistic and cultural space of Uzbek, about language as the basis of national identity. Development of dialogical and

monologue oral and written speech, communication skills, moral and aesthetic feelings, abilities for creative activity.

The methodological foundations of the study were the provisions of philosophy about the meaning, the social nature of language as a means of communication; theories of scientific knowledge on the reflection and transformation of objective reality, the use of theoretical and empirical approaches in the research process; the relationship of language and consciousness, thinking and speech; the place and role of language in the mental and spiritual development of the individual; transition of quantitative changes into qualitative ones; relationship between theory and practice; cultural-historical, culturological, systemic, communicative - activity approaches to the development of speech and the formation of speech culture of the individual; general scientific provisions of systems theory for a systematic consideration of the logic of research and complex issues of the problem under study; a synergetic approach to interpreting the development of scientific knowledge; Theoretic statements about speech as a sign activity, the unity of speech content and linguistic form, the interdependence of the sensual and the rational in language acquisition, the priority role of speech in the development of a linguistic personality; mechanisms for generating statements; theories of the content of language education; position on the formation of a linguistic personality; legislative acts, concepts.

In domestic pedagogical research, the attention of scientists is drawn to various aspects of this process. Scientists note that a high level of speech culture becomes the most important professional and personal quality of a teacher. The full manifestation of the professional qualities of an elementary school teacher is reflected precisely by means of speech. A teacher can realize himself in different life roles, correct the course of interpersonal communication, effectively demonstrate his professionalism, ensuring the effectiveness and efficiency of his activities. In the light of the foregoing, the problem of the formation of speech culture in the process of professional training of future primary school teachers is actualized.

However, despite the close attention to this issue from domestic scientists, the problem under consideration, with all the significance of the results of scientific research, advanced pedagogical experience, is insufficiently studied, which is explained by the lack of a holistic approach to the development of the speech culture of the future. primary school teacher in the course of his professional training; insufficiently defined didactic, content, organizational and methodological support of the process of development of the speech culture of the future elementary school teacher; the dominance in the content of professional training of a specialist of the information, rather than the activity-practical component of this process; insufficiently identified pedagogical conditions, contributing to an increase in the effectiveness of the formation of speech culture both at the level of the content of the students' activities, and at the level of integration of linguistic and psychological and pedagogical knowledge; lack of optimization in the implementation of active teaching methods that have a problematic and cultural orientation; the insufficiency of using the potential of subject-subject interaction in the educational process of the university.

The development and improvement of speech culture is one of the necessary conditions for the formation of a worldview, the development of aesthetic taste, and raising the professional level. The teacher's knowledge of sign systems can testify to the formation of the teacher's speech culture; the ability to produce cultural texts with their help in the process of communication; ability to take into account social, ethical norms and roles, professional attitudes, value orientations. The

listed knowledge, skills and abilities are at the same time the goal of education and a means of forming the general culture of the individual. The communicative-speech personality of future primary school teachers includes at least three characteristics that determine such a personality trait as communicative-speech competence: a) practical possession of an individual stock of verbal and non-verbal means for updating information, and pragmatic functions of communication; b) the ability to vary communication means in the process of communication due to changes in situational conditions; c) the construction of statements and discourses in accordance with the norms of the chosen communicative code and the rules of pedagogical ethics.

Speech culture, which forms the basis of the general professional competence of future primary school teachers, is a method and form of social integration, organization, self-identification, socialization of the individual, which determine the potential of the education system, the measure of its impact on the development of the student's personality. The success of the interaction between the subjects of the educational process (teacher and student) is determined by the level of communicative and speech culture of an adult as an obligatory component of a holistic pedagogical process, means and conditions for the implementation of all functions and types of professional activity.

The formation of the speech culture of future primary school teachers as a necessary and important part of the educational process is a complex of targeted pedagogical influences, the purpose of which is to transfer to students knowledge about the world around us, social experience gained in the process of cultural and historical development of society, and also the development of socially acceptable and socially approved forms of communicative speech behavior. Building an effective system the topic of the formation of a communicative and speech culture with the inclusion of new didactic, informational means requires theoretical knowledge of the laws by which the learning process proceeds. The external patterns of the learning process characterize its dependence on external processes and conditions: the socio-economic, political situation, the level of culture of the whole country, the needs of society in a certain type of personality and the level of its education and culture in a given historical period. Internal patterns include links between the components of the pedagogical process: goals, content, methods, means, forms of education.

The growing interest of pedagogical science in the study of such a phenomenon as speech culture is evidenced by a number of terms that have appeared recently: "speech skill" (V.P. Chikhachev), "educational pedagogical speech" (Yu.V. Rozhdestvensky [5]). N. I. Formanovskaya expresses precisely about the importance of theoretical and practical work on the development of speech culture of all segments of the population: "It is absolutely necessary to urgently, broad, mass education of people in those aspects and directions which already have a more or less reliable base, speech culture, stylistics, rhetoric, communication theory" [6, p. 3].

It should be noted the increased interest of scientists in the problem of the development of speech culture. The term "speech culture" is a set of knowledge, abilities, skills that provide an easy construction of speech statements for the optimal solution of communication problems. The fundamental in speech culture is speech, in which the main quality is the correctness of language norms, speech usage, the quality of the content of speech communication, the quality and ethics of communicative intentions. This is a type of activity of members of society, manifested in the use of language in the processes of communication and thinking. Speech is the brightest attribute of the life activity of each individual, representing the level of his general development and culture.

The speech culture of a person is one of the components of a general culture, is associated with a culture of thinking, feelings, a culture of behavior, largely determines the quality of the moral education of a person, and affects the effectiveness of communicative activity. Speech is considered as a phenomenon not only linguistic, but also psychological, ethical and aesthetic. Even in ancient Rome, attempts were made to create a theory and qualities of good speech, a theory of language and style. M. B. Golovin created a system, classified the qualities of good speech. The scientist gave a theoretical explanation and description of the main qualities of speech, their structural and linguistic properties and features, the consistency of their connections, the consistency of terminological designations through the analysis of the correlation of speech with non-speech structures: speech - language, speech - thinking, speech – consciousness.

Turning to the phenomenon of "speech culture", we rely on the theory of speech activity, which in modern psychology and linguistics is interpreted from the standpoint of the general theory of activity. Speech activity is a set of psychophysical works of the human body necessary for the construction of speech (M.B. Golovin), a specific component of any type of human activity [4]. In the pedagogical theory of speech activity, speech culture is considered as one of the most important indicators of a person's spiritual wealth, the culture of his thinking, as a means of personality development.

Speech culture (culture of language proficiency) is such a choice and such an organization of language means that, taking into account the situation of communication and observing proper linguistic, communicative and ethical norms, can provide the greatest effect in achieving the set communicative goals.

The absolutization of one of the aspects of the culture of speech leads researchers to create separate disciplines or "teachings" that claim a decisive place within the framework of linguistic culture

Thus, the formation of the speech culture of future primary school teachers becomes relevant in two aspects: as the speech culture of the teacher's personality, where the correct, literate, figurative, beautiful speech of the teacher is a role model for his students; and as mastering the tools and technologies for its formation among elementary school students.

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